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Integrated DSS system

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Preface

This report is prepared within the framework of the OPTIMUS – OPTIMising the energy USE in cities with smart decision support system (OPTIMUS) (608703), supported by the 7th Framework Programme, under the Objective ICT-2013.6.4 Optimising Energy Systems in Smart Cities. OPTIMUS aims to design, develop and implementation a Decision Support System (DSS) addressed to city authorities, in order to assist them to optimize the energy use in their premises and reduce CO₂ emissions.

Summary

This deliverable refers to task 3.5 of the project. This task has the purpose of integrating the different modules developed within the project. The modules integrated are: the semantic framework, data portal, analysis tools, inference engine, management and the end-used environments.

This document presents the internal architecture of the OPTIMUS DSS and the interrelations of its different components. The outcomes of this task have been the OPTIMUS DSS operative with the different components integrated and an installation guide to deploy the OPTIMUS DSS in the pilot cities.

Deliverable structure

The document is divided into three main sections:

- The “OPTIMUS DSS internal architecture” which presents the different modules of the DSS and how they are interrelated.
- The “Data flows” that describes three data flows: from sources to Virtuoso server, from Virtuoso server to prediction models, and from Prediction models to inference rules.
- The “Installation guidelines” that explains how to install and setup the different modules

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1 Introduction

This document summarises the outcomes of Task 3.5 *Integration and Development of OPTIMUS DSS* which is part of WP3 *Semantic Data Integration and Development of OPTIMUS DSS*. The purpose of this task is the integration of the different components developed in WP3, in particular: the semantic framework (Deliverable 3.1 *Published data in an open data portal*), data portal (Deliverable 3.4 *Functional end-user web-based environments*), analysis tools (Deliverable 3.2 *Analysis tools to process data and inference rules*), inference engine (Deliverables 3.2 and Deliverable 3.3 *Inference engine integrated in the management environments*), management (Deliverable 3.4) and the end-used environments (Deliverable 3.4).

This document presents the internal architecture of the OPTIMUS DSS and the interrelations of its different components.

The outcomes of this task have been the following:

- An operative OPTIMUS DSS with the different components integrated.
- An installation guide to deploy the OPTIMUS DSS in the pilot cities.

1.1 Interconnection between Tasks

The work carried out in Task 3.5 integrates the DSS modules carried out in other deliverables:

- The data capturing modules description reported in Deliverables 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5, and 2.6.
- The semantic framework described in Deliverable 3.1
- The prediction models and inference rules presented in Deliverables 3.2 and 3.3.
- The front-end environments reported in Deliverable 3.4.

2 OPTIMUS DSS internal architecture

OPTIMUS DSS is composed of different modules developed within the project as well as of other modules which have been implemented with already existing open source solutions. Figure 1 shows the OPTIMUS DSS internal architecture. The modules in blue are those developed within the project and the grey ones those implemented using third-party solutions.

Data capturing modules. These are modules that capture data from the sources and send it to the semantic framework. A module has been developed to gather data from each source: weather forecasting, de-centralized sensor-based, social media, energy prices, and renewable energy sources. Each module has been developed with a particular technological solution. For example, the weather forecasting and the energy prices module have been developed as a Java applications while the renewable energy module is a Python

application. The description of each module can be found in Deliverables 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5, and 2.6. The data captured by each module are:

- **Weather forecasting:** data concerning the forecast of weather conditions as well as weather data from control units.
- **De-centralized sensor-based:** data regarding energy and environmental performance, obtained through sensors.
- **Social media:** data from building occupants regarding comfort.
- **Energy prices:** data about energy prices from the day-ahead market.
- **Renewable energy production:** data about the production of energy from renewable energy sources.

Semantic framework. It consists of the communication infrastructure built with semantic web technologies whose goal is to facilitate the transferring of data from the distributed sources, and the subsequent contextualization of the raw data in specific contexts. The semantic framework is based on the publish-and-subscribe communication pattern and it has been implemented with the Ztreamy system, a semantic service which processes the data with the purpose of contextualizing them, and the Virtuoso triple-store, a data repository. The semantic service has been implemented as a Python application. The semantic framework is described in Deliverable 3.1.

DSS engine. The goal of the DSS engine is to propose an Action Plan to the end-user. To do so, the intelligent rules have to be fed with predicted, real-time and static data. The DSS engine encompasses the prediction models –implemented as RapidAnalytics processes, the inference rules, and a MariaDB database to store the results. The inference rules have been implemented as a Symfony PHP web application. The technical description of the prediction models and inference rules can be found in Deliverable3.2 and Deliverable3.3.

DSS environments. The DSS has three environments for different kinds of users. A data portal environment for citizens and third-parties to navigate through the data, end-user environments for energy managers of the buildings to visualize monitored data and the Action Plans, and the management environments for technical users to setup the DSS. The data portals have been implemented using Elda. The end-user and management environments have been implemented as a Symfony PHP web application. The technical description of the environments can be found in Deliverable 3.4.

Figure 1: OPTIMUS DSS internal architecture

3 Data flows

There are several data flows between the modules of the OPTIMUS DSS. In this section we present the main data flows including the inputs and outputs of the modules, the interrelations, and the processing tasks.

3.1 From data sources to Virtuoso server

The data is obtained from different sources, and transformed and stored as monitored data on the Virtuoso server (Figure 2). This flow mainly takes place through the data capturing modules and via the semantic framework. Basically, the process can be summarized as follows:

- The data sources are external entities which contain the raw data such as sensors, weather conditions services, and energy prices agency.
- The data capturing modules –developed in WP2– gather raw data from the sources.

- The raw data is transformed into RDF using the OPTIMUS ontology described in Deliverable 3.1.
- The RDF data is communicated to the DSS by means of the semantic framework, in particular thanks to the Ztreamy server.
- The semantic service contextualizes the RDF data and stores it on Virtuoso server as monitored data.

At the end of the process, the Virtuoso server contains monitored data processed, contextualized, and modelled according to the OPTIMUS ontology. A technical description of this flow can be found in deliverable 3.1.

Figure 2: Data flow from the sources to the triple store

3.2 From Virtuoso server to prediction models

The prediction models are fed with monitored data in order to forecast an indicator (Figure 3). The modules involved in this flow are the semantic framework and the DSS engine, in particular the RapidAnalytics and MariaDB database. The process can be summarized as follows:

- It starts with the monitored data that has been stored on Virtuoso server in the previous data flow.
- The data is obtained by the semantic framework by means of SPARQL queries. The queries are specific for each prediction model, resulting in a one-to-one relation.
- The RapidAnalytics processes –which implement the prediction models– ask the semantic framework for the data.
- The RapidAnalytics processes apply the prediction models using the monitored data. The results of the process are stored in the MariaDB database as predicted data.

At the end of the process, the MariaDB database contains predicted data for the relevant indicators to understand the behaviour of a building. A technical description of the prediction models can be found in Deliverable 3.2.

Figure 3: Data flow from monitored data to the predicted data

3.3 From prediction models to inference rules

The monitored and predicted data are used by the inference rules to suggest an Action Plan (Figure 4). The modules involved in this flow are the semantic framework and the DSS engine, in particular the PHP services (inferences rules) and the MariaDB database. The process is the following:

- It starts with predicted data –which has been stored in MariaDB database in the previous data flow– and the monitored data is available on the Virtuoso server.
- The data is obtained by the semantic framework. In the case of accessing Virtuoso server, it is done by means of SPARQL queries while when accessing through Maria DB, it is done via MariaDB. The PHP services –which implement the inference rules– ask the semantic framework for the data.
- The PHP services invoke the inference rules using the monitored and predicted data. The results of the process are stored in MariaDB database as action plans.

At the end of the flow, the Actions Plans have been stored in the MariaDB database. A technical description of the inference rules can be found in Deliverable 3.3.

Figure 4. Data flow from monitored and predicted data to the action plans

4 Installation guidelines

The OPTIMUS DSS is composed of several modules which need to be installed separately. The software needed to deploy the OPTIMUS DSS includes the following:

- Java 7
- PHP 5.6
- Web server (Apache, Internet Information Services)
- Python 5.7
- Virtuoso vcr 110

- Ztreamy 0.3
- RapidAnalytics Community Edition 1.3

4.1 Semantic framework installation

The semantic framework is composed of an instance of a Ztreamy server and the semantic service. Both are Python scripts.

Ztreamy server is configured with a file which specifies the port used by the server and the list of streams (Figure 5).

The name of the streams follows a pattern described in Deliverable 3.1. Moreover, each stream is linked to its data capturing module through its name. For example, the variable “stream_EPro1” is assigned to the first stream of the energy production capturing module.

```
[global]
port=9000

[streams]
stream_EPro1= santcugat_townhall_pv_irradiation
stream_EPro2= santcugat_townhall_pv_power

stream_EPri1= spanish_electricity_energycost
stream_EPri2= spanish_gas_energycost

stream_SM1= santcugat_townhall_social_twitter
stream_SM2= santcugat_townhall_social_facebook

stream_WF1= savona_weatherforecast_air_temperature_forecast
stream_WF2= savona_weatherforecast_relative_humidity_forecast

stream_DCD1= savona_school_bmssiemens_environmentalsensor
stream_DCD2= savona_school_bmssiemens_energymeter
```

Figure 5: Configuration file of a Ztreamy server

The semantic service is a subscriber that receives data from a Ztreamy server. It is important that Ztreamy and the semantic service use the same stream names. The configuration of the semantic service starts with the URL which Ztreamy is installed. Then, the URL of the triple store and the graph which will be used to store the RDF data are set. Next, the number of streams per each data capturing module is specified. Finally, the configuration of the log is completed.

A list of prefixes, common to all RDF data sent by the data capturing modules, is set. The last section of the configuration file is devoted to setting up the streams. For each stream, the name and the parameters used by semantic service to contextualize the data are specified. For example, “owl_sensingdevice_class” refers to the class name of the sensor which is measuring the data, and “owl_observedproperty_class” to the class name of the property

measured by the sensor. The streams need to have the same name in the Ztreamy configuration file.

```
[global]
ztreamy_server = http://arcdev.housing.salle.url.edu:9000/
sparq_endpoint_url = http://winarc.housing.salle.url.edu:8080/sparql
sparq_endpoint_graph = http://optimus-test-pro
## Energy production streams
epro_number_streams = 4
## Energy prices streams
epri_number_streams = 10
## Social Media streams
sm_number_streams = 2
## Weather forecast streams
wf_number_streams = 18
## De-centraliced data streams
dcd_number_streams = 14
#log_level: 0 no log, 1 only errors, 2 all log
log_level = 2

[prefixes]
ssn = <http://purl.oclc.org/NET/ssnx/ssn#>
xsd = <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>
time = <http://www.w3.org/2006/time#>
semanco = <http://semanco-tools.eu/ontology-
releases/eu/semanco/ontology/SEMANCO/SEMANCO.owl#>
optimus = <http://optimus-smartcity.eu/ontology-releases/eu/semanco/ontology/optimus.owl#>

#####
## SANT CUGAT - TOWN HALL - PV panels - Irradiation
[stream_EPro1]
stream = santcugat_townhall_pv_irradiation
owl_sensingdevice_class = optimus:SunnyPortal_SolarRadiation
owl_sensingdevice_uri = sunnyportal_solar_radiation
owl_observation_uri = sunnyportal_solar_radiation
owl_featureofinterest_uri = solar_irradiation
owl_featureofinterest_class = optimus:Solar_IrradiationFeature
owl_observedproperty_uri = solar_irradiation
owl_observedproperty_class = semanco:Solar_Irradiation
owl_sensoroutput_class = optimus:Solar_IrradiationSensorOutput

...
```

Figure 6: Configuration file of semantic server

4.2 RapidAnalytics installation

The prediction models have been implemented as RapidAnalytics processes running on a RapidAnalytics server. In this way, these processes can be invoked remotely as a web service. The processes can be uploaded to the RapidAnalytics server with the RapidMiner

desktop application. Once the processes are in RapidAnalytics, they can be published as web services.

The list of available web services can be seen in the option “Processes>>Services” of the left menu (Figure 7).

Figure 7: RapidAnalytics web interface

When a web service is created, it is important to take into account the parameter binding section. The parameters that a web service can accept have to match the input parameters of the process (Figure 8).

Figure 8: RapidAnalytics. Parameter binding

4.3 OPTIMUS DSS setup

In order to setup a DSS instance in a pilot city, the following steps have to be carried out using the administration environment described in Deliverable 3.4.

1. Creating a new building with description data such as address, year of construction, surface, and building use.
2. Creating building partitions according to the actual building. For example, the building is divided into floors, sections, and rooms (Figure 9). This is important because the action plans can only be applied to building partitions. So, if a room is going to be affected by an Action Plan, then this room should appear in the building partitioning.

Figure 9: Management environment. Building partitioning

3. Adding the sensors which should have already been installed through the semantic framework. The sensors configured in the building should also be present in the Ztreamy and semantic service configuration file. The URI of the sensor (Figure 10) should match the "owl_sensingdevice_uri" parameter. Moreover, in every sensor, a web service to invoke a prediction model, can be set up. Usually, not all the sensors will have a prediction model.

Figure 10: Management environment. List of sensors

- Enabling the Action Plans to be used in the building. Once the plans have been enabled, they should be configured for every partition. To do so, every plan has a predefined list of input data that has to be mapped to the sensors (Figure 11). One sensor can be mapped to more than one plan, such as the outdoor temperature.

Figure 11: Management environment. Action Plan management.

5 Conclusions

A first version of the OPTIMUS DSS has been assembled. This version integrates the components developed across the different tasks of the project. The integration of the modules developed by the different partners using diverse technologies and programming languages, has been an authentic challenge. This has required to work simultaneously in the different modules: data capturing modules, semantic framework, DSS engine, DSS environments.

The DSS presented in this report will be the base of the implementation of the demonstration scenarios to be carried out in the third year. The DSS functionalities will be tested in real scenarios in the three pilots. Also, at the moment it is being explored in which ways the DSS could be implemented in other cities.

It remains to be done the integration in the DSS of the equipment that could not be installed at time of writing this document. Moreover, the feedback from the demonstration activities in real conditions with real users will be used to tune and enhance the OPTIMUS DSS.